

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at AICRIP, India, 1978.

Variety	Life span (days)		Infective insects (%)	Retention (days)		Infected seedlings		
	Long-est	Av ^a		Long-est	Av	%	No./insect	No./infective insect
TN1	18	6.4 a	95	4	1.8	37	1.60	1.68
IR26	7	5.6 ab	80	3	1.4	26	1.10	1.38
Habiganj DW8	8	5.2 ab	80	3	1.4	35	1.15	1.44
Pankhari 203	14	4.8 bc	75	2	1.1	22	0.80	1.07
Latisail	8	4.8 bc	75	3	2.2	30	1.25	1.67
Kataribhog	8	4.8 bc	75	2	1.3	24	1.00	1.33
Ambemohar 159	8	4.2 cd	85	3	1.6	38	1.40	1.65
Ptb 18	8	3.7 cd	85	2	1.5	40	1.25	1.47
IR34	8	3.7 cd	70	1	1.0	22	0.70	1.00
Gam Pai 30-12-15	8	2.8 d	75	1	1.0	27	0.75	1.00
Max or av	18	4.6	80	4	1.4	30	1.10	1.37

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

DW8, IR26, and TN1 (see table).

About 30% of 729 seedlings inoculated by the viruliferous insects became infected. There seemed to be no remarkable differences among the 10 rice varieties as far as tungro transmission was concerned. However, the insects were

less efficient in transmitting the tungro virus to IR34, Gam Pai 30-12-15, and Pankhari 203 than to the other varieties (see table). Those three might be more resistant to tungro than the others in the test. ■

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at IRRI, Philippines

K. C. Ling and M. S. A. Miah, International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines

As part of the RTV Collaborative Project, an IRRI study investigated the life span and tungro transmission of *Nephotettix virescens* in the IRRI greenhouse from 15 May to 28 June, 1978. In two

trials, 800 adult insects — 40 females and 40 males on 10 varieties — were given an acquisition access time of 4 days on tungro-diseased seedlings. The insects survived 1 to 23 days. The average life span was 4.8 days (5.0 days for female insects, and 4.6 days for the male).

The short life span on IR34, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Ptb 18, and Pankhari 203 indicated that these varieties were more resistant to the insect than were the six others in the test (see table).

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at IRRI, Philippines, 1978.

Variety	Life span (days)		Infective insects (%)	Retention (days)		Infected seedlings		
	Long-est	Av ^a		Long-est	Av	%	No./insect	No./infective insect
Habiganj DW8	23	7.3 a	14	1	1.0	3	0.14	1.00
Kataribhog	14	7.2 a	18	2	1.2	4	0.19	1.07
IR26	12	5.9 b	81	4	1.6	31	1.24	1.52
TN1	15	5.7 b	89	4	1.5	36	1.28	1.44
Ambemohar 159	19	5.5 b	48	3	1.2	16	0.56	1.18
Latisail	13	5.4 b	71	5	1.5	27	0.99	1.39
Pankhari 203	11	3.8 c	5	2	1.3	2	0.05	1.00
Ptb 18	9	2.6 d	45	2	1.0	18	0.45	1.00
Gam Pai 30-12-15	6	2.6 d	48	2	1.0	20	0.49	1.03
IR34	6	2.3 d	54	2	1.0	25	0.55	1.02
Max or av	23	4.8	47	5	1.5	18	0.60	1.17

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

Of 2,637 seedlings of 10 rice varieties inoculated by the insects, 18% developed tungro. Insect efficiency in transmitting the tungro virus was lowest with Pankhari 203, Habiganj DW8, and Kataribhog. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Anatomical studies of rice varieties tolerant of and susceptible to complete submergence at seedling stage

S. Karin and B. S. Vergara, Plant Physiology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Leaf sheath and leaf blades from 12 varieties were collected in 10-day-old seedlings to study the anatomical differences between varieties tolerant of the susceptible to complete submergence.

The number of vascular bundles on the first and second leaf blades varied among the varieties; however, the difference between the tolerant and susceptible varieties was not significant.

The leaf sheath is characterized by the presence of a large air space which alternates with the vascular bundles and is separated by narrow bands of parenchyma. The number of vascular bundles in the first and second leaf sheaths of the tolerant and susceptible varieties did not show any difference or correlation to submergence tolerance.

The role of the air space in submergence has not been studied. It possibly is important because it may serve as an oxygen reservoir or, if the leaf tips are above the water level, as passageway for transporting oxygen from the leaf blade to the roots. Thus, the air space might play an important role in maintaining the integrity of the cells. On the other hand, the occurrence of large air spaces may result in spongy, weak leaf sheaths that would make the plant prone to lodging when the water level recedes.

The percentage of air space per unit area was negatively and significantly correlated to submergence tolerance ($r = -0.5997^*$). The air spaces on the first leaf

sheath already were developed at the time of submergence. In the second leaf sheath, the susceptible varieties showed earlier development of air space and had more of it than the tolerant varieties 10 days after seeding. The total number of air space in the first and second leaf sheath also was correlated negatively to

submergence tolerance ($r = -0.6657^*$).

The number of layers and thickness of the sclerenchyma layer of the first leaf sheath of the rice seedlings tested did not correlate with submergence tolerance. However, the tolerant varieties FR13A and Nam Sagui 19 showed one layer more than the other varieties. There are

variations in thickness in both tolerant and susceptible varieties.

Anatomically, the main significant difference between tolerant and susceptible varieties was in the percentage of the area occupied by air space and the number of air spaces. The more susceptible varieties had more air spaces. ■

Effect of flash flood on performance of some rice varieties

S. Biswas, S. Mallik, and S. S. Pradhan, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah 712102, West Bengal, India

An adaptive trial with eight popular, longduration entries was conducted at Block Seed Farm, Panskura, Midnapore District, West Bengal during 1978 kharif. These rainfed lowland entries represented tall indicas (NC1281 and OC1393), semidwarf cultivars (CR1014, CR1009, IET5656 and Pankaj) and a new semitall selection, CN540, along with Mahsuri.

Thirtyday-old seedlings of each cultivar were planted at 20- x 10-cm spacing in a 50-m² area during mid-July. The crop was deeply submerged by an unprecedented flood at 70 days after transplanting (end Sep) in 1978. The water depth was 3 m and the crop remained fully submerged for 10 days. Immediately after the flood water receded, it appeared that all the varieties had perished. But varieties with

Table 1. Effect of flash flood on the performance of some rice genotypes.

Variety	Hills counted (mean no.)	Hills surviving (mean no.) after flooding	Damaged hills (%)	Panicles (mean no./m ²)
CN540	49	43	12.24	152
Mahsuri	49	39	20.40	129
CR1014	49	33	32.65	85
IET5656	49	29	40.81	60
CR1009	49	9	81.63	9
OC1393	49	Nil	100.00	Nil
NC1281	49	Nil	100.00	Nil
Pankaj (check)	49	15	69.38	11

regenerative capacity subsequently developed fresh tillers from the live culms. After panicle emergence in the regenerated tillers, data on percentage of surviving culms and different yield attributes (number of tillers, panicle length, plant height, flag leaf length, number of fertile grains per panicle, exertion and total number of nodes per plant) were taken.

The two tall indicas, viz, NC1281 and OC1393, had no surviving culms, CN540 had 87.76% live hills after postflood regeneration and produced the most

panicles per square meter (Table 1). In terms of panicle yield per plant, panicle length, and number of filled grains per panicle, CN540 performed better than Mahsuri (Table 2). CR1009 produced a few panicles under similar conditions, but showed maximum sterility (88.65%).

CN540 represents a semitall plant type with long slender grains (9.7 x 2.3 mm). Its superior performance in rainfed lowland and flash-flood conditions might be an advantage over Mahsuri, a variety that has gained considerable popularity during kharif in India. ■

Table 2. Mean performance of 6 rice varieties with respect to different characters.

Variety	Panicle yield (g/plant)	Tillers (no./plant)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Flag leaf length (cm)	Fertile grains (no./panicle)	Sterile grains (no./panicle)	Exsertion (cm)	Nodes (no./plant)	Fertile-sterile grain ratio (F:S)
CN540	4.66	3.97	125.21	22.53	23.26	79.33	12.00	3.44	10.23	6.61
Mahsuri	3.08	3.14	119.07	16.35	18.03	62.93	9.21	4.20	10.06	6.83
CR1014	2.24	2.64	113.46	18.10	22.05	68.26	25.59	5.53	10.40	2.66
IET5656	1.60	2.15	83.73	15.67	15.86	35.88	13.22	—	11.23	2.71
CR1009	1.22	1.07	75.48	14.83	16.26	20.80	36.17	1.16	10.26	1.12
Pankaj (check)	0.85	0.86	76.81	15.69	19.44	42.11	22.05	0.73	9.33	1.90
LSD (0.05)	1.25	1.16	4.15	2.90	1.94	7.97	4.75	1.47	1.90	

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.